

Metal Ion Interactions with some Antibiotic Drugs of Penicillin Family. Part-IV. Equilibrium Study on the Complex Formation of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Zinc(II) with Ampicillin

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Combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric study on the complex formation of M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni$ and Zn) with ampicillin, (α -*d*-(-)aminobenzylpenicillin), $ampH^{\pm}$ at 37° in aqueous solution at a fixed ionic strength, $I = 0.1 M NaNO_3$, provided evidence of formation of complexes of the types: $M(amp)^+$, $M(amp)_2$, $M(H_{-1}amp)$, $M(H_{-1}amp)(amp)^-$ and $M(H_{-1}amp)_2^2-$. Ambidentate nature of the ligand and the possible mode of its coordination with the M^{2+} ions at different pH values were elucidated.

Penicillin group of pharmaceuticals show antibiotic properties by virtue of their ability to inhibit protein synthesis¹. Biological metal ions play key roles in the structural organisation and activation of certain enzymes, which are involved in transfer of genetic information from DNA, leading to the synthesis of specific proteins. Metal ions are also known to stabilise the appropriate conformation of the ribosome, where the actual synthesis of the proteins takes place². Therefore, the study of complexation equilibria of metal ions with the fragments of nucleic acids, proteins etc. in the presence of antibiotic drugs³, may be useful on one hand, in elucidating the mechanism of action of the drug itself and designing newer and superior drugs having fewer or no side-effects or after-effects. The present paper describes the results of equilibrium study on the complex formation of some bivalent transition metal ions, viz. Co, Ni and Zn with a commonly used form of penicillin, viz. α -*d*-(-)aminobenzylpenicillin (1), which is popularly known as ampicillin (hereafter, $ampH^{\pm}$). Such study with Cu^{2+} ion has yielded interesting results⁴.

ampH[±]

1

Results and Discussion

Zwitterionic nature, $ampH^{\pm}$, of the ligand ampicillin was established from the study⁴ of its deprotonation equilibria in the absence of M^{2+} ions.

Complex formations of the ligand with the M^{2+} ions were observed at $pH > 4$, where the ligand was exclusively in the $ampH^{\pm}$ form. pH-metric titrations of Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} - $ampH_2^+$ mixtures could not be continued above pH 8 due to commencement of precipitation. Ni^{2+} - $ampH_2^+$ mixture, on the other hand, remained clear even above pH 11 and consequently it was extensively studied. The 1 : 5 $Ni^{2+} : ampH^{\pm}$ mixture was light yellow around

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of (1 : 5) Ni²⁺-ampH[±] mixtures at different pH in aqueous solution; I = 0.1 M NaNO₃ at 37°, path length = 1 cm, [Ni²⁺] = 0.003 M, [ampH[±]] = 0.015 M.

pH 6.6 (λ_{\max} 495, 465 and 415 nm). With rise of pH (~8.0) the yellow colour intensified and a slight blue-shift of the λ_{\max} values (490, 460 and 410 nm) were observed (Fig. 1). Study of the composition of complex formed in the mixture, by Job's method of continuous variation⁵ indicated 1 : 1 Ni²⁺ : amp⁻ complex at pH 6.6 and 1 : 2 complex at pH 8.0. A plot of \bar{n} (average number of H⁺ released due to the reaction of Ni²⁺ ion with ampH[±]) vs pH (Fig. 2) also showed the stepwise nature of the complex formation equilibria. The \bar{n} , pH plot showed zero slope at pH 6–6.5 (\bar{n} = 1) and at pH 7.5–8 (\bar{n} = 2), which indicated the formation of Ni(amp)⁺ and Ni(amp)₂ complexes at these pH values according to equilibria (1) and (2) respectively,

$$K_{\text{Ni(amp)}}^{\text{Ni}} = \frac{[\text{Ni(amp)}^{+}]}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}][\text{amp}]}$$
 (1)

$$K_{\text{Ni(amp)}_2}^{\text{Ni(amp)}} = \frac{[\text{Ni(amp)}_2]}{[\text{Ni(amp)}^{+}][\text{amp}]}$$
 (2)

Analogous nature of \bar{n} , pH plots of the corresponding Co²⁺ and Zn²⁺ systems before the start of precipitation indicated the formation of similar type of complexes. The most possible mode of coordination of the ligand in the M(amp)⁺ and M(amp)₂ complexes should be through the amino nitrogen atom and the carbonyl oxygen atom of

the amide bond, like the corresponding Cu²⁺ complexes⁴.

With rise of pH (>8.0) the 1 : 5 Ni²⁺ : ampH[±] mixture gave another buffer region (8.0 ≤ pH < 11.0) with the release of two more protons per Ni²⁺ in overlapping steps. The only possible source of proton release might be the metal-promoted deprotonation⁶ of the amide moiety in the Ni(amp)⁺ and Ni(amp)₂ complexes according to equilibria (3)–(5),

$$K_{\text{Ni(amp)}}^{\text{H}} = \frac{([\text{H}][\text{Ni(H}_{-1}\text{amp)}])}{[\text{Ni(amp)}^{+}]}$$
 (3)

$$K_{\text{Ni(amp)}_2}^{\text{H}} = \frac{([\text{H}][\text{Ni(H}_{-1}\text{amp(amp)}^{-})])}{[\text{Ni(amp)}_2]}$$
 (4)

$$K_{\text{Ni(H}_{-1}\text{amp(amp)}^{-})}^{\text{H}} = \frac{([\text{H}][\text{Ni(H}_{-1}\text{amp)}_2^{2-}])}{[\text{Ni(H}_{-1}\text{amp(amp)}^{-})]}$$
 (5)

The H₋₁amp²⁻ ligand species in these complexes, meant the fully deprotonated ampH[±] ligand, i.e. amp⁻ minus the amide proton. Deprotonation of

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of Ni²⁺-ampH[±] equilibria : (1) ampH₂⁺, (2) ampH[±], (3) amp⁻, (4) Ni²⁺, (5) Ni(amp)⁺, (6) Ni(amp)₂, (7) Ni(H₋₁amp), (8) Ni(H₋₁amp)(amp)⁻, (9) Ni(H₋₁amp)₂²⁻ and (10) \bar{n} , pH.

the amp^- ion into $\text{H}_1\text{amp}^{2-}$ within the coordination complex involved a structural change of the type, involving the substitution of the amide carbonyl oxygen atom by the deprotonated amide nitrogen

Fig. 3. pH-titration curves of ampH^\pm in the absence and in the presence of metal ions in aqueous solution of ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3) at $37 \pm 0.1^\circ$: (1), 0.005 M HNO_3 ; (2), (1) + $0.001 \text{ M Co(NO}_3)_2$; (3), (1) + $0.001 \text{ M Ni(NO}_3)_2$; (4), (1) + $0.001 \text{ M Zn(NO}_3)_2$; (5), (1) + 0.005 M ampH_2^+ ; (6), (5) + $0.001 \text{ M Co(NO}_3)_2$; (7), (5) + $0.001 \text{ M Ni(NO}_3)_2$; (8), (5) + $0.001 \text{ M Zn(NO}_3)_2$.

atom. This also brings the thiazolidine sulphur atom of the ligand in a position suitable for providing axial coordination to the Ni^{2+} ion, leading to a change from $\text{Ni(O=CNH)(NH}_2)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4$ or $\text{Ni(O=CNH)}_2(\text{NH}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ to $\text{Ni}(\overline{\text{NC=O}})(\text{NH}_2)(\text{S})-$

$(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3$ or $\text{Ni}(\overline{\text{NC=O}})_2(\text{NH}_2)_2(\text{S})_2$ systems respectively ($2 \rightleftharpoons 3$).

The formation constants of $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})$, $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})(\text{amp})^-$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})_2^{2-}$ complexes were calculated using the relations,

$$\log \beta_{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})}^{\text{Ni}} = \log K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})}^{\text{Ni}} + \log K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})}^{\text{H}} \quad (6)$$

$$\log \beta_{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})(\text{amp})}^{\text{Ni}} = \log K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2}^{\text{Ni}} + \log K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2}^{\text{H}} \quad (7)$$

$$\log \beta_{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})_2}^{\text{Ni}} = \log K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2}^{\text{Ni}} + \log K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2}^{2\text{H}} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{where, } K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2}^{2\text{H}} = K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2}^{\text{H}} \times K_{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})(\text{amp})}^{\text{H}}$$

These types of amide deprotonated complexes could not be identified with Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} due to precipitation, possibly of electroneutral $\text{M}(\text{amp})_2$, $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$ or $\text{M}(\text{OH})(\text{amp})$ complexes around pH 8. However, a very small amount ($< 5\%$) of $\text{Co}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})$ complex was formed before precipitation. In calculating the formation constants using the SCOGS⁷ programme, the species, viz. ampH_2^+ , ampH^\pm , amp^- , M^{2+} , $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$, $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{M}(\text{amp})^+$, $\text{M}(\text{amp})_2$ and $\text{M}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})$ for Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} were considered to occur in the complexation equilibria. For Ni^{2+} - ampH_2^+ system, the hydroxo species $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})^+$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ were omitted as the formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2$ was complete at pH values much lower than that of the hydrolytic equilibria of Ni^{2+} (aq) ions and as no precipitation was observed in the entire pH range of titration.

Both $\text{M}(\text{amp})^+$ and $\text{M}(\text{amp})_2$ complexes dominated the region of biological pH, with the latter complex contributing more than 50% of the total metal ions. Amide deprotonated complexes could be identified only with the Ni^{2+} - ampH^\pm system. $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_1\text{amp})(\text{amp})^-$ complexes occurred in significant amounts at $\text{pH} > 8.0$ and dominated the region between $\text{pH} 9.0$ and 10.0 . At still higher pH values, the concentration of

the fully depro-tonated complex, $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})_2^{2-}$, increased sharply. This indicated the existence of an additional complexation equilibria (9),

The formation constant, $K_{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp}) + \text{amp}^-}^{\text{H}}$, was calculated with the aid of the relation,

$$\log K_{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp}) + \text{amp}^-}^{\text{H}} = \log \beta_{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})_2}^{\text{Ni}} + \log K_{\text{amp}^-}^{\text{H}} - \log \beta_{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})}^{\text{Ni}} \quad (10)$$

using the computer refined values of $\beta_{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})}^{\text{Ni}}$, $\beta_{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})_2}^{\text{Ni}}$ and the estimated value of amide deprotonation constant $K_{\text{amp}^-}^{\text{H}}$ (i.e. $K_{(-\text{CONH-})}^{\text{H}}$) of the ligand amp^- ion.

(N, $\bar{\text{N}}$, S) coordination by the $\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp}^{2-}$ ligand species in the amide deprotonated complex (3) is favoured by delocalisation of π -electron density of the Ni^{2+} (d^8) ion over to the vacant $d\pi$ orbitals of the sulphur donor atom of the ligands, leading to an increase of electronegativity of the coordinated Ni^{2+} ion⁴. A direct consequence of such $\text{Ni} \rightarrow \text{S}(\pi)$ bonding in the $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})_2^{2-}$ complex is the relative magnitudes⁸ of the successive amide deprotonation constants of the complex, $\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2$. Contrary to the general expectation, the second step deprotonation constant $K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})^-}$ was higher than the first step constant $K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2}^{\text{H}}$ by about 1.25 in log units. The successive stability constants, $K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})}^{\text{Ni}}$ and $K_{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2}^{\text{Ni}(\text{amp})}$ of the $\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2$ complex, however, showed the usual order, possibly due to the absence of sulphur coordination in the $\text{Ni}(\text{amp})^+$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{amp})_2$ complexes.

Experimental

Ampicillin trihydrate, $\text{ampH}^{\pm} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [99%; Aldrich mol. wt. 403.46, m.p. 198–200°, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20}$ (+)247° (c = 1, H_2O)] was directly used. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade and

their solutions were prepared in double-distilled freshly boiled and cooled, CO_2 -free water. Always freshly prepared solutions of ampH^{\pm} were used though there was no change of the uv absorption spectrum⁴ of ampH^{\pm} on preserving its 0.005 M aqueous solution in a refrigerator for several days.

The following solutions each of initial volume of 25 ml were prepared for the pH metric study : (i) 0.005 M HNO_3 ; (ii), (i) + 0.001–0.002 M $\text{M}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ [M = Co, Ni and Zn]; (iii), (i) + 0.005 M ampH^{\pm} in the form of ampH_2^+ ; (iv), (iii) + 0.001–0.002 M $\text{M}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. Ionic strength of all the solutions were held constant, $I = 0.1$ M, by adding requisite amounts of NaNO_3 . The solutions were allowed to attain equilibrium at the experimental temperature ($37 \pm 0.1^\circ$) and were titrated with a carbonate-free standard 0.1 M aqueous NaOH solution⁹ having the desired ionic strength and maintained at the same temperature. The procedure for the pH-metric study was the same as described earlier¹⁰. Some representative data are presented in Fig. 3.

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS* WITH AMPICILLIN IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

Temp. = $37 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $I = 0.1$ M NaNO_3				
Constant	H^+	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Zn^{2+}
$\text{p}K_{\text{LH}_2}^{\text{H}}$ (i.e. $\text{p}K_{\text{COOH}}^{\text{H}}$)	2.50	—	—	—
$\text{p}K_{\text{LH}}^{\text{H}}$ (i.e. $\text{p}K_{\text{NH}_3^+}^{\text{H}}$)	7.05	—	—	—
$\text{p}K_{\text{L}}^{\text{H}}$ (i.e. $\text{p}K_{(-\text{CONH-})}^{\text{H}}$)	13.37 (calc.)	—	—	—
$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{amp})}^{\text{M}}$	—	3.12	3.66	2.98
$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{amp})_2}^{\text{M}(\text{amp})}$	—	2.56	3.02	2.54
$\log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{amp})_2}^{\text{M}}$	—	5.68	6.68	5.52
$\text{p}K_{\text{M}(\text{amp})}^{\text{H}}$	—	9.40	8.50	—
$\text{p}K_{\text{M}(\text{amp})_2}^{\text{H}}$	—	—	10.52	—
$\text{p}K_{\text{M}(\text{amp})_2}^{2\text{H}}$	—	—	19.79	—
$\log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})}^{\text{M}}$	—	-6.28	-4.84	—
$\log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})(\text{amp})}^{\text{M}}$	—	—	-3.84	—
$\log \beta_{\text{M}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp})_2}^{\text{M}}$	—	—	-13.11	—
$\log K_{\text{M}(\text{H}_{-1}\text{amp}) + \text{amp}^-}^{\text{H}}$	—	—	-21.64	—

* Limits of error in the constants : ± 0.05 in log units. Other constants used : $\text{p}K_{\text{w}} = 13.62$ at 37° (Ref. 12), $\text{p}K_{\text{Co}}^{\text{H}} = 8.21$, $\text{p}K_{\text{Co}}^{2\text{H}} = 17.29$, $\text{p}K_{\text{Zn}}^{\text{H}} = 7.84$, $\text{p}K_{\text{Zn}}^{2\text{H}} = 14.87$ (Ref. 10).

pH-titration data as were the averages of three titrations, were used for the calculation of the formation constants by the computer programme, SCOGS⁷. Preliminary values of some of the equilibrium constants were evaluated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹¹. Refined values of the constants are presented in Table 1. Complexation equilibria were elucidated by analysing the concentration distribution curves (Fig. 2).

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References

1. N. S. EGOROV in "Antibiotics—A Scientific Approach", MIR Publishers, Moscow, 1985, Chap. 8.
2. G. L. EICHHORN in "Inorganic Biochemistry", ed. G. L. EICHHORN, Scientific Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 1973, Vol. 2, Chaps. 33, 34; D. D. PERRIN and R. P. AGARWAL in "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", ed. H. SIGEL, Marcel-Dekkar, 1973, Vol. 2, p. 167; G. L. EICHHORN, *Nature*, 1962, **194**, 474; F. R. BATCHELOR, F. P. DOYLE, J. H. C. NAYLER and G. N. ROLINSON, *Nature*, 1959, **183**, 257.
3. R. B. MARTIN in "Frontiers in Bioinorganic Chemistry", ed. A. V. XAVIER, VCH, Weinheim, 1986, p. 71; H. SIGEL in "Frontiers in Bioinorganic Chemistry", ed. A. V. XAVIER, VCH, Weinheim, 1986, p. 84.
4. G. N. MUKHERJEE and T. K. GHOSH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 1033.
5. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim. Paris*, 1928, **9**, 113.
6. H. SIGEL and R. B. MARTIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **82**, 325; H. GAMP, H. SIGEL and A. D. ZUBERBUHLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 1190; T. A. KABANOS and J. M. TANGARIS, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1984, **13**, 89; G. N. MUKHERJEE and P. K. CHAKRABORTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, **24**, 841; S. P. MCGLYNN, T. AZUMI and D. KUMAR, *Chem. Rev.*, 1981, **81**, 475.
7. I. G. SAYCE, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 1397; 1970, **18**, 653; I. G. SAYCE and V. S. SHARMA, *Talanta*, 1972, **19**, 831.
8. G. N. MUKHERJEE, P. DHAR and A. SEN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 3022.
9. G. SCHWARZENBACH and W. BIEDERMANN, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1948, **31**, 331.
10. G. N. MUKHERJEE and T. K. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 194.
11. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
12. J. LURIE, "Handbook of Analytical Chemistry", MIR Publishers, Moscow, 1978, p. 198.

